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REVIEW ON LAGHU NIGHANTU – AN IMPORTANT AYURVEDIC LAXICON

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Abstract

Nighantus are one of the most important traditional works in the field Ayurveda, especially in the study of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*. It acts as a lexicon of drugs and *Dravya*, defining its synonyms and indication in various diseases. *Dravyaguna vijnana*'s main focus is on the qualities, uses, and identification of herbal plants in various disorders. Laghu Nighantu is synonymous type of work; this work was composed by Vyasa Keshava Rama in 18th century A.D. There are 159 drugs have been mentioned in this Nighantu.

Key Words:

Ayurveda, Dravyaguna, Laghu Nighantu, Vyasa Keshava Rama

INTRODUCTION:

Nighantu is a vocabulary or glossary of words. It is depicted that without Nighantu a physician is like a scholar without grammar and archer is without practice of archery. Nighantu may be defined as a glossary containing synonyms, name of drugs, plants, animals, minerals or anything that is administered either for food or medicine. The Nighantu contained synonyms which throw light on different aspects of the entity and thus expose their hidden meaning. The ancient Nighantu were actually like *Kosa* containing synonyms of *Dravya*. But later on, concept of Nighantu changed and added their properties, actions and uses of *Dravyas*.¹

The *Laghu Nighantu* is a work consisting of about 500 lines. The name *Laghu Nighantu* is mentioned at the end as well at the beginning of the manuscript. At the end of the manuscript, it is stated that this *Laghu Nighantu* is a part of *Ausadhinamamala*. This may indicate that *Ausadhinamamala* is a work by the same author of which *Laghu Nighantu* is a part from that text. *Namamala* is said to be a common name for lexicons by different authors, particularly *Dhanvantari Nighantu* and others. *Laghu Nighantu* is a lexicon of the synonymous type, which gives the different synonyms for one drug together with their properties mentioned in text. This work was composed by *Vyasa Keshavaram*. *Laghu Nighantu* is one of the works on *Dravyaguna* during modern period. This work deals with individual *Dravya*, with their synonyms *Guna* and *karma*.²

Author of *Laghu Nighantu*:

The author of this *Nighantu* is *Vyasa Keshava Rama* as mentioned in the manuscripts. There are no other references to be found about this author in any of the existing literature on *Nighantu*. There are no references regarding the place or family. In his manuscript, he has shown preference to Gujarati names. On this reference it may be assumed that the author possibly belonged to some place round about Gujarat and was possibly a traditionally practitioner of *Ayurveda*.³

Date of *Laghu Nighantu*:

In the absence of any internal and external evidence, it is not possible to come to a conclusion regarding the date of the author. It may generally be stated that the author may belong to the end of the 18th century A.D.⁴

Text of *Laghu Nighantu*:

This *Nighantu* is also a synonymous type of work like other *Nighantu*. The way of presentation is very simple and the matters followed is *Anushtupa*. This lexicon does not disclose any original contribution but it merely lists some very commonly used remedies in general practice. Totally 159 drugs have been mentioned in this lexicon, drugs belong to vegetable kingdom and mineral kingdom are described here. Except *Kasturi*, no other drug belonging to animal kingdom is mentioned. The first drug dealt in this work is *Guduci*. The heading is given as *Galonama*. *Galo* is a Gujarati name for *Guduci*. In the same way *Elaci* for *Ela*, *Pipara* for *Pippali* etc. It is observed that the common vegetables like *Anantamula*, *Vidanga*, *Lodhra* etc are not mentioned in this work. It is also noted that the drugs like *Ahiphena*, *Katuvira*, *Bhanga* and *Yasthimadhu* which are introduced in *Nighantu* literature earlier by *Madanapala* and others, are not found in this work. It is possible that the object of writing this *Nighantu* was to acquaint the readers of most commonly used drugs and these omitted drugs may not be common in use.⁵

At the end useful appendixes have been given:

- In the 1st appendix the original text of *Laghu Nighantu* has been given as it is.
- In the 2nd appendix details of the matters used in *Laghu Nighantu* have been given.
- In the 3rd appendix, an index of synonyms of substances mentioned in *Laghu Nighantu* has been given in alphabetical order
- In the 4th appendix, an index of scientific names of plants available in *Laghu Nighantu* has been given.
- In the 5th appendix, a picture gallery of plants available in *Laghu Nighantu* has been presented.

- In the appendix, a list of those reference books and a glossary have been given, which have been used in text correction and interpretation etc.⁶

Description of drug

The classification is as follows⁷:

No.	Name of Drug	Botanical name	Family	Synonym	Guna
1	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	<i>Menispermaceae</i>	<i>Amrutlata, Nagakanyaka, Devanirmita, Shyama</i>	<i>Tridosha nashak, Grahini, Ushna, Dipaniya, Jawara, Trushna, Daha, Kamala, Vatarakt anashak.</i>
2	<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i>	<i>Ranunculaceae</i>	<i>Bhangura, Madri, Shrungika</i>	<i>Vishwa, Tikta Rasa, Tridosha, Atisara, Sopha, Shoola, Jwaranas haka, Deepan- Pachan, Grahi</i>
3	<i>Suksma ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Kapot Chandra Indrika, Tuttha</i>	<i>Varna, Bala, Krumi, Kasa, Swas, Hikka, Prameha.</i>
4	<i>Bruhad ela</i>	<i>Amomum subulatum</i>	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Chandraela, Mahaila, Sambhuta, Kanyaka, Pruthavika</i>	<i>Swarg Granthi, Raktapitt a, Vaman, Shukrash marinash ak</i>
5	<i>Nagkeshar</i>	<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	<i>Clusiaceae</i>	<i>Nagakinjalka, Hemakanchan</i>	<i>Ibha, Visha, Visharp, Raktados ha, Harllash, Kushthan ashak</i>
6	<i>Twak</i>	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>	<i>Lauraceae</i>	<i>Varang, Choch, Sinhayogadeva,</i>	<i>Bhrunga, Kapha, Kasa, Vata-</i>

				<i>Maheshwara</i>	<i>Shamak</i>
7	<i>Tamal patra</i>	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>	<i>Lauraceae</i>	<i>Palash, Chhadan, Chhad, Roma, Tapasaja, Vaas, Vastra, Anshuka, Patarak.</i>	<i>Kapha, Vatarakt a, Hrullash, Arochakt anashak</i>
8	<i>Vansh rochan</i>	<i>Bambusa bambos</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	<i>Vainavi, Shubhra</i>	<i>Kashay, Madhura, Tikta, Kshaya, Swas, Bhramna shak</i>
9	<i>Tav kshir</i>	-	-	<i>Pakaya, Yavashastiksamhv</i>	<i>Same as Vansh Rochan</i>
10	<i>Sushavi</i>	-	-	<i>Kunchika, Pruthavi, Vrushchikli, Vashvika</i>	<i>Katuvipa k, Kruminas hak, Agnideep ak</i>
11	<i>Dadima</i>	<i>Punica granatum</i>	<i>Punicaceae</i>	<i>Kuttima, Karak, Shukavallabh</i>	<i>Madhura, Vaman, Trushna, Daha, Atisarana shak</i>
12	<i>Dhanyak</i>	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Chhatradhanya, Vitunnaka, Kushtumbaru, Alhachi, Hradyagandh, Vedhak</i>	<i>Swasa, Kasa, Kshaya, Arsha, Trusha, Chhardi, Jwaranas hak</i>
13	<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>	<i>Piperaceae</i>	<i>Bahubeeja, Kshudra Tandula</i>	<i>Vata, Kapha, Swas, Kasanash ak</i>
14	<i>Pippalimool</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>	<i>Piperaceae</i>	<i>Kutilashira</i>	<i>Malabhedak, Tikshna, Ushna, Vaman and Kaphajanya, Shoolana shak</i>
15	<i>Chavya</i>	<i>Piper</i>	<i>Piperaceae</i>	<i>Chavan, Valli,</i>	-

		<i>retrofractum</i>		<i>Manabh. Markati</i>	
16	<i>Gajapippali</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum</i>	<i>Piperaceae</i>	<i>Gajavalli, Karikana, Hashtika</i>	<i>Tridosha, Vaman, Anaha, Shoola, Agniman dhyahara</i>
17	<i>Chitrak</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	<i>Plumbaginaceae</i>	<i>Pathina, Daruna, Dhananjay, Marjara</i>	<i>Ushna, Shopha, Arsha, Krumi, Kushthan ashak</i>
18	<i>Sunthi</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Katu shreshta</i>	<i>Agnideep an, Vrushya, Grahi, Vata, Kapha, Shoola, Trushna, Amavata, Pandu, Slipadan ashak</i>
19	<i>Marich</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i>	<i>Piperaceae</i>	<i>Dharmapatan, Shirovrut, Muddal</i>	<i>Pittavard hak, Tikshna, Ruksha, Rochana, Deepan, Katu Vipaka and Rasa, Kaphana shak, Laghu</i>
20	<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	<i>Araceae</i>	<i>Golomi, Ikshukarnika</i>	<i>Pachan, Deepan, Ushnavir ya, Bhutabad ha, Apasmar a, Shula, Un mada, Adhman, Vataroga</i>
21	<i>Lavang</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	<i>Myrtaceae</i>	<i>Shreepushpa, Varisambhav, Shekhar</i>	<i>Vishanas hak, Tikshna,</i>

					<i>Chakshushya, Bhaktarochan, Vata-Pittanashak, Shital, Snighdha, Murdhvajaroga</i>
22	<i>Mansi</i>	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i>	<i>Valerianaceae</i>	<i>Kryyadi, Tapaswini</i>	<i>Kashayrasa, Piita, Vrana, Kaphanashak</i>
23	<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Aucklandia costus</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Pakala, Vaniraja, Kaubher</i>	<i>Tikta-Madhura Rasa, Vata-Kapha, Vishanashak</i>
24	<i>Tagar</i>	<i>Valeriana jatamansi</i>	<i>Valerianaceae</i>	<i>Jihya, Kalanushari, Nahush, Patav.</i>	<i>Kushtha, Twakaroga</i>
25	<i>Kasturi</i>	-	-	<i>Mrugandaja, Vedhamukhya, Gandhachelika</i>	<i>Sugandhita, Ksharyukta, Chakshushya, Mukharoganshak</i>
26	<i>Karpuram</i>	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i>	<i>Lauraceae</i>	<i>Tuhina, Himavaluka, Shitabhra, Shitalaraja</i>	<i>Madhura, Katu, Tikta Rasa, Netraroga, Mukharoga, Trusha, Mukhavairashya, Kapha, Shopha, Atisara, Varana, Dahasaman</i>
27	<i>Jatipatri</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	<i>Myristicaceae</i>	<i>Sumana, Malanashini, Malati</i>	<i>Mukharoganshak</i>

					,Hridya, Vata- Kaphana shaka
28	<i>Jatiphal</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	<i>Myristicaceae</i>	Same as <i>Jatipatri</i>	Same as <i>Jatipatri</i>
29	<i>Dhatur</i>	<i>Datura metel</i>	<i>Solanaceae</i>	<i>Dhurta, Dhushtura, Kitava, Devata, Tulaphala</i>	<i>Dushitar aktadosh a,Pitta, Vrana,Vi shahara</i>
30	<i>Kirataka</i>	<i>Swertia chirayita</i>	<i>Gentianaceae</i>	<i>Hema, Anaryatikta, Ramasenak, Maladhvanshi, Naipal, Sannipatari</i>	<i>Vatakara k, Ruksha, Kapha- Pittajany a, Jawara, Glani, Nindra, Krumi, Sannipat ahara</i>
31	<i>Vasak</i>	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	<i>Acanthaceae</i>	<i>Sinha Parni, Vrush, Shitavalli</i>	<i>Vaman, Kasa, Raktapitt anashak</i>
32	<i>Katuki</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>	<i>Scrophulariaceae</i>	<i>Rishta, Vibha, Dwijangika</i>	<i>Malabhe dak, Ruksha, Kapha- Pittaja Jwaranas hak</i>
33	<i>Shathi</i>	<i>Hedychium spicatum</i>	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Sugandhamoola, Vadhu</i>	<i>Vata, Kapha, Swasa, Kasa, Hikka, Jwaranas hak</i>
34	<i>Devdaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>	<i>Pinaceae</i>	<i>Kilim, Snehavidha, Surahya</i>	<i>Katuvipa ka, Snigdha, Ushnavir ya, Vatasha mak</i>
35	<i>Katrunm</i>	<i>Cymbopogon schoenanthus</i>	<i>Poaceae</i>	<i>Sakala, Dhyamak, Patal, Bhushtruna</i>	<i>Katu, Tikshna, Ushana, Vatanash</i>

					<i>ak, Mukhaso dhak</i>
36	<i>Shrungi</i>	<i>Pistacia chinensis</i>	<i>Anacardiaceae</i>	<i>Mahaghosha, Chandraspada</i>	<i>Kapha-Vatanash ak, Hikka, Jwara, Kasanash aka</i>
37	<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	<i>Zingiberaceae</i>	<i>Gauri, Varavarnini, Bhadralata, Harita, Vrusheshta</i>	<i>Prameha, Apachi, Pittadosha, Twakavik ar, Krumi, Pandu, Kapha, Pitta, Sopha, Kandu, Kushtha, Jwaranas hak</i>
38	<i>Darvi</i>	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	<i>Berberidaceae</i>	<i>Pachampcha, Parjanya, Hemakanta</i>	Same as <i>Haridra</i>
39	<i>Ajamoda</i>	<i>Apium graveolens</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Lochamarkat, Khrahya</i>	<i>Swasa, Kasa, Bastiroga</i>
40	<i>Yavanak</i>	<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Barbari, Kharpushpa</i>	<i>Tridoshan ashak, Shitasham ak, Agnidipak a</i>
41	<i>Parasik yavani</i>	<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i>	<i>Solanaceae</i>	<i>Chauhar, Karmani</i>	<i>Katu, Hridya, Pathya, Atisarana shak</i>
42	<i>Kuberak</i>	-	-	<i>Sugandhakarabh, Bahira</i>	Same as <i>Parasik Yavani</i>
43	<i>Hingu patri</i>	-	-	<i>Bilwika, Charupatrika</i>	<i>Katu, Tikshna, Ushnavir ya, Krumi, Kaphash amak</i>

44	<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ferula narthex</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Agoodhgandha, Shupadhupana</i>	<i>Vata, Kapha, Anaha, Shulanas haka, Pittaprapak opaka</i>
45	<i>Sharkara</i>	-	-	<i>Ahichhatra</i>	<i>Murchha, Moha, Jwara, Chhardi, Trusha, Daha, Mukhapa ka</i>
46	<i>Khand</i>	-	-	<i>Panshulaka</i>	-
47	<i>Guda</i>	-	-	<i>Rasala, Rasaja, Rasasambhav</i>	-
48	<i>Bhargi</i>	<i>Rotheca serrata</i>	<i>Verbenaceae</i>	<i>Bhramara, Barba, Bhramara, Bhramarpriya</i>	<i>Swasa, Kasa, Jwaranas hak</i>
49	<i>Soma valka</i>	<i>Morellaesculenta</i>	<i>Myricaceae</i>	<i>Kaidarya</i>	<i>Mukharoga, Kasa, Swasa, Jwara</i>
50	<i>Shatpushpa</i>	<i>Anethum graveolens</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Madhavi, Shifa</i>	<i>Vata and Rakta-Atisara Nashak</i>
51	<i>Jirak dwaya</i> 1. <i>Sweta</i> 2. <i>Krishana</i>	1. <i>Cuminum cuminum</i> 2. <i>Carum carvi L.</i>	<i>Apiaceae</i>	<i>Kanajiraka Pruthavi</i>	<i>Snigdha, Hima, Vaman, Daha, Vatapitta nashak, Katu, Kaphavat anashaka</i>
52	<i>Rasona</i>	<i>Allium sativum L.</i>	<i>Lilliaceae</i>	<i>Arishta, Mahaushadh</i>	<i>Patra-Kshariya, Madhura Madhya Bhaga-Madhura, Picchila, Adho Bhaga-Ushna, Tikshna, Katu</i>

					<i>Vipaka and Rasa Keshya, Hridaya, vrushya, agnidipaka, Guru, Kilasa, Kushta, Arsha, Prmeha, Krumi, Kasa, Swasa, Kapha-Vatanashak</i>
53	<i>Palandu</i>	<i>Allium cepa L.</i>	<i>Lilliaceae</i>	<i>Yavaneshta, Sukanda, Vaktradushan</i>	<i>Pitta Prakopak</i>
54	<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Solanum virginianum L.</i>	<i>Solanaceae</i>	<i>Kantali, Dushpraghrsha, Dhavani, Hemapushpika</i>	<i>Sawas, Kasa, Jwara, Vatanashak</i>
55	<i>Bruhati</i>	<i>Solanum anguivi Lam.</i>	<i>Solanaceae</i>	<i>Rashtrika, Vishada, Mahotika, Sinhika</i>	-
56	<i>Vidari</i>	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i>	<i>Laguminiaceae</i>	<i>Charukanda, Vrushyakanda, Vidalika</i>	-
57	<i>Gokshur</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris L.</i>	<i>Zygophyllaceae</i>	<i>Trika, Bhakshak</i>	<i>Vrushya, Vatanashak, Mutrashodhak, Madhura Rasa and Vipaka, Mutrakrucca, Ashmari</i>
58	<i>Bilwa</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	<i>Rutaceae</i>	<i>Goharitaki</i>	<i>Pathya, Rakta Atisaranshak</i>
59	<i>Dhanvyas</i>	<i>Alhagi maurorum Medik.</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Tamramuli</i>	<i>Shital, Tikta, Swas, Trivra Jwara, Visarp,</i>

					<i>Prameha, Kushta, Rakta Atisara, Pitta Atisarana shak</i>
60	<i>Khadira</i>	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	<i>Mimosaceae</i>	<i>Gayatri, Kshitidrum</i>	<i>Kushta, Visarp, Prameha, Pittajwara, Vishphot a, Vicharchi ka, Krumirog a, Galaroga</i>
61	<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus L.</i>	<i>Cyperaceae</i>	<i>Jalada, Varah, Kroda, Rajakaseruk, Vrushdhvankshi</i>	<i>TiktaRasa, Sangrahi, Agnideep an, Pachan, KatuKas hay, KaphaPit ta, Raktados ha, Twakaro ga, Shosh, Arsh, Atisarana shak</i>
62	<i>Satala</i>	<i>Euphorbia pilosa L.</i>	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Amala, Maralika, Dipta</i>	-
63	<i>Prsarini</i>	<i>Sida veronicaefolia Lam.</i>	<i>Tiliaceae</i>	<i>Bhadrakali, Bhadrabala, Rajabala</i>	-
64	<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	<i>Scrophulariaceae</i>	<i>Somavallari, Matshyakshi</i>	-
65	<i>Suran</i>	<i>Amorphophallus campanulatus</i>	<i>Acraceae</i>	<i>Chitradandak</i>	-
66	<i>Vruddh daruk</i>	<i>Argyreia nervosa</i>	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	<i>Jirnavaluka, Jirnavallari, Rukshagandha</i>	-
67	<i>Sauvarchala</i>	-	-	<i>Manduki, Varada, Adityavallabha, Mandukparni,</i>	-

				<i>Sukhodbhava</i>	
68	<i>Bhrungraj</i>	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Angarak, Bhekraj, Bhrung</i>	-
69	<i>Kasmard</i>	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i>	<i>Caesalpiniaceae</i>	<i>Kaal, Kanak</i>	-
70	<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus L.</i>	<i>Araceae</i>	<i>Vijaya, Ikshukarnika</i>	-
71	<i>Sweta vacha</i>	<i>Paris polyphylla Sm</i>	<i>Melanthiaceae</i>	<i>Medhya, Shadgrntha, Haimvati</i>	-
72	<i>Vastuka</i>	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	<i>Shakvira, Tamrapushpa, Prvalak</i>	-
73	<i>Palankya</i>	<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	<i>Kshurika, Madhusudani</i>	-
74	<i>Jivanti</i>	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i>	<i>Asclepiadaceae</i>	<i>Yashakari, Jivavardhini</i>	-
75	<i>Amla lonika</i>	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	<i>Oxalidaceae</i>	<i>Changeri, Lonika</i>	-
76	<i>Loni</i>	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	<i>Portulacaceae</i>	<i>Naredramata Ambastha, Kshudramli</i>	-
77	<i>Tanduliya</i>	<i>Amaranthus polygonoides</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	<i>Vishahari, Alpamarish</i>	-
78	<i>Shitivarak</i>	<i>Celosia argentea</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	<i>Kashamari, Bhuranji, Suchipatrak</i>	-
79	<i>Mulakam</i>	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum subsp.</i>	<i>Brassicaceae</i>	<i>Sekimo, Neelkanth, Bastika</i>	-
80	<i>Chankyamoolak</i>	-	-	<i>Markat, Shaley</i>	-
81	<i>Hilamochi</i>	<i>Enhydra fluctuans</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Jalabrahmi, Sankhdhara</i>	-
82	<i>Kalambi</i>	<i>Ipomoea aquatic forssk.</i>	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	<i>Vayasi, Shatparva</i>	-
83	<i>Karvalli</i>	<i>Momordica charantia L.</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Katilla, Mruduparnak</i>	-
84	<i>Patola</i>	<i>Trichosanthes dioica Roxb.</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Kaphahara, Amrutaphala</i>	-
85	<i>Karkotak</i>	<i>Momordica dioica Roxb.</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Tiktaparna, Sugandhak</i>	-
86	<i>Kushmand</i>	<i>Benincasa hispida cogn.</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Karkaru, Valliphalavar</i>	-
87	<i>Tumbi</i>	<i>Lagenaria siceraria standl</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Kshatriyavara, Mahaphaala</i>	-
88	<i>Chirbhati</i>	<i>Cucumis melo L.</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Iravaru, Vyalpatrika</i>	-
89	<i>Karkati</i>	<i>Cucumis utilisissimus Roxb.</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Mutraphala, Chhardini</i>	-
90	<i>Bimbi</i>	<i>Coccinia indica</i>	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	<i>Golha, Tundikerphal</i>	-
91	<i>Basta gandha</i>	<i>Thymus</i>	<i>Lamiaceae</i>	<i>Shakambhara,</i>	-

		<i>serpyllum L.</i>		<i>Putimayurika</i>	
92	<i>Pushkarmool</i>	<i>Inula racemosa Hook.</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Dhira, Brahmaturthak</i>	-
93	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula Retz.</i>	<i>Combretaceae</i>	<i>Himatja, Kalika</i>	<i>Kashayrasa, Ushnavirya Ruksha, Lavanrahit, Laghu, Agnideepan, Medhya, Ayurvedhak, Kushtha, Krumi, Pandu, Prameha, Plihodara, Jalodara nashak</i>
94	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Shadarasa, Parvakita, Makandi</i>	Same as <i>Haritaki</i>
95	<i>Bibhitaki</i>	<i>Terminalia bellirica Roxb.</i>	<i>Combretaceae</i>	<i>Samvartak, Harya, Kalka</i>	Same as <i>Haritaki</i> and <i>Amalaki</i>
96	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica A.juss</i>	<i>Meliaceae</i>	<i>Niyaman, Vanarpriya, Chhardighna, Hinguniryas, Pittasara, Ravipriya</i>	<i>Tikta Rasa, Kapha, Vaman, Vrana, Hrillash, Kushthan ashak.</i>
97	<i>Parpat</i>	<i>Fumaris indica</i>	<i>Papaveraceae</i>	<i>Kavach, Pittavidhvansi</i>	<i>Pitta, Hridayroga, Daha, Jwara Nashak. Drys Kapha</i>
98	<i>Hiberam</i>	<i>Pavonia zeylonica</i>	<i>Malvaceae</i>	<i>Jala, Keshnamak, Pingal</i>	<i>Vaman, Hrillash, Trushna, Atisara, Krumi</i>

99	<i>Shalparni</i>	<i>Pleurolobus gangeticus</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Dhruva, Vidarigandha</i>	-
100	<i>Pushtiparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta Desv.ex</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Pruthak Parni, Vishnuparni, Hariparni</i>	Both Parni Laghu, Madhura, Malabhedak, Pitta-Vata Shamak
101	<i>Agnimanth</i>	<i>Premna serratifolia L.</i>	<i>Verbenaceae</i>	<i>Vhanimanth</i>	Guru, Tikta, Vata, Shofa and Amanashak
102	<i>Erand</i>	<i>Ricinus communis L.</i>	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Sweta Erand- Vyadamba, Rubuk, Rubu Rakta Erand- Triparna, Dwiparnak</i>	<i>Vrushya, Guru, Atyant Madhur, Shodhak, Swas, Varhm, Pliharoga, Anaha, Udara Roga, Tridosha, Antrashola Nashak, Majja-Vardhmaroga, Antrasopha, Kapha, Vata, Adhaman, UdaraRoganashak, Malabhedak</i>
103	<i>Manjistha</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia L.</i>	<i>Rubiaceae</i>	<i>Janavallabha, Tamraka</i>	<i>Kushtha, Visharp, Sophanashak, Varnaday</i>

					<i>ak, Karna-Netra Roga, Meha, Pitta, Rakta Atisarana shak</i>
104	<i>Aragwadha</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Caesalpiniaceae</i>	<i>Pragrah, Arevat, Kapotanda, Pamavinashan, Dadruvinashan</i>	-
105	<i>Gugullu</i>	<i>Commiphora mukul</i>	<i>Burseraceae</i>	<i>Naktachar, Pura</i>	<i>Katu, Kashay, Ushnavirya, Meda, Shopha, Apachi, Vaman, Granthiroga, Gulma, Prameha, Kushtha, Krumi, Vata, Kapha, Kleda, Amavata nashak</i>
106	<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i>	<i>Asteraceae</i>	<i>Sarpgandha, Rogaha</i>	<i>Ushna Virya, Vata-Shophan ashak, Sarvrogha hara</i>
107	<i>Shatavari</i>	<i>Asparagus racemosa</i>	<i>Liliaceae</i>	<i>Variyasi, Urdhvakantali, Tungi</i>	<i>Vata-Pitta and Kapha Shamak, Increase Virya</i>
108	<i>Kharparam</i>	-	-	<i>Ritipushpa</i>	<i>Tridosha nashak, Chakshushya, Shulanas hak</i>
109	<i>Vankultathika</i>	<i>Cassia absus L.</i>	<i>Leguminosae</i>	<i>Kulali, Aranyakulatthika</i>	<i>Chakshushya,</i>

					<i>Netrarog anashak</i>
110	<i>Aswagandha</i>	<i>Withania somnifera L.</i>	<i>Solanaceae</i>	<i>Turagi, Hayi, Vanavasini</i>	<i>Balya, Virya Vardhaka, Kasa, Swas, Kshayan ashak</i>
111	<i>Kutaja</i>	<i>Holarrhena pubescens Wall</i>	<i>Apocynaceae</i>	<i>Kautaja, Kota Kutajabija-Shakrahya, Kalingaka</i>	<i>Kushtha, Pitta, Raktavik ara, Tvagados ha, Arsha, Atisarana shak</i>
112	<i>Punarnava</i>	<i>Boerhavia diffusa L.</i>	<i>Nyctaginaceae</i>	<i>Prayrushenya, Vrushketu</i>	<i>Ushnavir ya, Malabhe dak, Shopha, Udararo ganashak</i>
113	<i>Indravaruni</i>	<i>Citrullus colocynthis L.</i>	<i>Curcubitaceae</i>	<i>Mrugairvaru, Balakpriya</i>	<i>Kaphana shak, Tiktarasa, Kruminas hak, Virechak</i>
114	<i>Taryman</i>	<i>Gentiana kurroo Royle.</i>	<i>Gentianaceae</i>	<i>Krutatrana, Varshiki</i>	<i>Agnideep an, Jirnajwar, Kamalas hamak</i>
115	<i>Yavkshar</i>	-	-	<i>Yavashuka, Paki</i>	<i>Gulma, Pliharoga, Panduro ga, Kaphana shak</i>
116	<i>Svarjikshar</i>	-	-	<i>Svarjika, Suvarchahya</i>	<i>Kapha, Gulma, Arsha, Vaman, Manda Agni, Vatanash ak</i>

117	<i>Tankan</i>	-	-	<i>Malatirasasambhava, Dravi, Dravan</i>	<i>Kaphanshak, Jatharag nivaradhak</i>
118	<i>Vjrak kshar</i>	-	-	<i>Ksharshrestha, Dhumottha, Dhumasara</i>	<i>Gulmoda ranashak and Same as Tankan</i>
119	<i>Saindhav lavana</i>	-	-	<i>Shilatmaka, Manimantha</i>	<i>Vibandha, Netraroga, Tridosha nashak</i>
120	<i>Ruchak lavana</i>	-	-	<i>Hridayagandhak, Krushnalavana</i>	<i>Gulmajny ashula, Vibandha nashak and Virechak</i>
121	<i>Vida lavana</i>	-	-	<i>Krutrimak, Dhurta, Asura</i>	Same as <i>Vidalavana</i>
122	<i>Samudra lavana</i>	-	-	<i>Rukshya, Ksharoddhinhav</i>	-
123	<i>Audbhida lavana</i>	-	-	<i>Vasuk, Gad</i>	-
124	<i>Dhulilavana</i>	-	-	<i>Valukail, Shailamulak</i>	<i>Katu, Malabhedak, Laghu</i>
125	<i>Kapikacchu</i>	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Bheri, Kandura</i>	<i>Vrushya, Pitta, Kapha and Malanas hak</i>
126	<i>Aparajita</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	<i>Fabaceae</i>	<i>Sweta-Katabhi Neela-Yonipushpi, Neelasyanda</i>	<i>Vata, Swasa Roga, Kasa, Kashay, Kilasana shak</i>
127	<i>Amra</i>	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	<i>Anacardiaceae</i>	<i>Kamanga, Malodbhva, Sahakar</i>	<i>Balaphal a-Vata-Pittakarak, Baddhas hthi-Kapha-Vatanash</i>

					<i>ak Pakwa-Guru, Madhur, Amla, Vata-Kapha, Shukrana shak</i>
128	<i>Jambuka</i>	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	<i>Myrtaceae</i>	<i>Mahaphal, Kakjambu</i>	<i>Guru, Vishtambhi, Shital, Atyantav atakarak, Mala-Mutrasan grahi, Akanthya, Kapha-Pittanashak</i>
129	<i>Puga phala</i>	<i>Areca catechu L.</i>	<i>Areaceae</i>	<i>Rasal, Kashay Kathina,</i>	<i>Swadu, Kashay, Kapha-Pitta, Mukharo ganashak</i>
130	<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	<i>Menispermaceae</i>	<i>Vruki, Prachina, Varuni</i>	<i>Atisarajanya Shula, Kapha-Pitta, Jwaranas hak</i>
131	<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum chelonoides</i>	<i>Bignoniaceae</i>	<i>Vasantduti, Alipriya</i>	<i>Kapha-Pitta, Raktados ha, Vaman, Trushna, Nidadhna shak</i>
132	<i>Tintuka</i>	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	<i>Bignoniaceae</i>	<i>Bhutivruksha, Mandukaparnak, Shona</i>	-
133	<i>Bija pura</i>	<i>Citrus medica L.</i>	<i>Rutaceae</i>	<i>Phalapuraka, Kesari</i>	<i>Twaka-Tikta, Katu, Kapha, Krumi, Vatanashak Mansa-</i>

						<p><i>Bruhana, Vata-Pittasha mak, Vrushya, Atyanat Guru Kesara-Amlarasa, Agnideep ana, Sawas-Kasa Roga, Gulma, Arsha, Udarash ula, Shoshnas hak Pushpa-Jatharag nivardha k</i></p>
134	<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Vitis vinifera L.</i>	<i>Vitaceae</i>	<i>Harhura, Sarasa</i>	<i>Kapila,</i>	<p><i>Dahanas hak, Vrushya, Chakshus hya, Rasa and Vipaka-Madhura, Snighdha, Kashay, Shitala, Guru, Vata, Raktapitt a Nashak, Mahatya y Janya Tiktashya tvnashak</i></p>
135	<i>Vata</i>	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Jati, Bahupada</i>		<p><i>Tridosha, Pittajanya Daha, Atisarana shak</i></p>
136	<i>Pippal</i>	<i>Ficus religiosa L.</i>	<i>Moraceae</i>	<i>Shyamala, Chalpatra</i>		<p><i>Raktapitt a, Sarva</i></p>

					<i>Atisarana shak, Sarpavis ha Nashak</i>
137	<i>Shami</i>	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i>	<i>Mimosaceae</i>	<i>Keshhantri, Sutunga</i>	<i>Guru, Madhur, Kesa, Atisarana shak</i>
138	<i>Rajadani</i>	<i>Manilkara hexandra Roxb.</i>	<i>Sapotaceae</i>	<i>Priyadarshana, Ravanika</i>	<i>Grahi, Vatakara k, Vranarop aka</i>
139	<i>Sleshmantak</i>	<i>Cordia myxa Roxb.</i>	<i>Boraginaceae</i>	<i>Shelu, Kruchtaru</i>	<i>Shital, Grahi, Ruksha, Picchal</i>
140	<i>Karir</i>	<i>Capparis decidua Edgew.</i>	<i>Capparaceae</i>	<i>Gudhadala, Malu</i>	<i>Vrana, Sopha, Yakrutar oga, Pliharog a, Malanas hak</i>
141	<i>Kolam</i>	<i>Ziziphus jujuba Lam.</i>	<i>Rhamnaceae</i>	<i>Badar, Kuval</i>	<i>Madhura , Amla, Pittavard hak, Vatanash ak and Dastava.</i>
142	<i>Akhukarni</i>	<i>Merrenia gangetica</i>	<i>Convolvulaceae</i>	<i>Shambarikarnika, Bhumichari</i>	<i>Tikta, Krumi, Yonidosh anashak</i>
143	<i>Sehund</i>	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i>	<i>Euphorbiaceae</i>	<i>Sudhadru, Nishintrashpatra</i>	<i>Gulma, Adhman, Pilhodar a, Kushtha, Prameha</i>
144	<i>Agaru</i>	<i>Aquilaria malaccensis Lam.</i>	<i>Thymelaeaceae</i>	<i>Durukashtha, Krumijagtha</i>	<i>Tikta, Ushna, Snigdha, Vata-Kaphana shak</i>
145	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa Kurz</i>	<i>Lythraceae</i>	<i>Kunjara, Madhyapavani</i>	-

146	<i>Gandhak</i>	-	-	<i>Rasadravi, Lelina</i>	-
147	<i>Manahshila</i>	-	-	<i>Gola, Manogna</i>	-
148	<i>Harital</i>	-	-	<i>Ala, Pinjara</i>	<i>Katu, Snigdha, Kashay, Visha-Kushtana shak</i>
149	<i>Sindoor</i>	-	-	<i>Raktarenu</i>	<i>Vrana, Kushthan ashak</i>
150	<i>Hingula</i>	-	-	<i>Chitranga, Darad</i>	<i>Vrana, Kushtha, Kruminas hak, Bala-Krantikar ak</i>
151	<i>Parad</i>	-	-	<i>Muktid, Harottha, Dhatunayak</i>	Mrutaparad-Jara-Mrutyuna shak Murcchit aparad-Vyadhish amak Bandha-Parad-Sawarg Praptikar , Krupakar ak
152	<i>Abhrak</i>	-	-	<i>Karoruha, Patal</i>	<i>Mrutyuhara, Vruddhav shtha-Palitanas hak</i>
153	<i>Suvarna</i>	-	-	<i>Chamikara, Shatkumbha, Jambunada</i>	<i>Dhatupushtikara, Smruti-Buddhivardhak, Vishadoshanashak</i> , <i>Bala-Krantikara, Swasa-Kasaroga</i> , <i>Netraroga</i>

154	<i>Rajat</i>	-	-	<i>Kaladhauta, Vasushreshth, Ruchira</i>	<i>Sukhakar ak, Buddhiva rdhak</i>
155	<i>Tamra</i>	-	-	<i>Udumbara, Traymbaka, Twashtra</i>	<i>Shodhita Tamra-Swasa-Kasanash ak, Siddhikar ak, Balavard hak</i>
156	<i>Apamarga</i>	<i>Achayranthes aspera</i>	<i>Amaranthaceae</i>	<i>Sankat</i>	<i>Tiktirasa, Kruminas hak, Shirshavi shodhan, Vamak, Raktasan grahi, Raktaatis aranasha k</i>
157	<i>Tejashvini</i>	<i>Celastrus paniculatus Willd.</i>	<i>Celastraceae</i>	<i>Mahaujasi, Kakandi, Kanguni</i>	<i>Katu, Medhya, Vishphot anashak</i>
158	<i>Ankola</i>	<i>Alangium salvifolium Wang</i>	<i>Cornaceae</i>	<i>Cheri, Kotar</i>	<i>Visha-Kushtana shak, Vamak, Virechak</i>
159	<i>Gambhari</i>	<i>Gmelina arborea Roxb.</i>	<i>Verbenaceae</i>	<i>Krushnavruntaka</i>	<i>Vata-Kapha, Sh opha, Me ha, Kruminas hak</i>

Characteristics of Laghu Nighantu:

- As the name “Laghu” suggests, it is relatively brief compared to other comprehensive lexicons.
- The first drug dealt in this work is *Guduci*. The heading is given as *Galonama*. Galo is a Gujarati name for *Guduci*. And here it is observed that importance is given to Gujarati names.
- Here drugs mentioned, are very commonly used in ayurved practice.
- *Paraya, Guna* and *Roghaghnta of commonly used drug*, are given here.
- Vegetable, animal and mineral kingdom drugs are mentioned in this Nighantu.
- Here *Prushanparni* is described as *Pushtiparni*. *Jyotishmati* is described as *Tejashvini*.
- 2 types of *Ativisha* are described in the text.
- There are 2 types of *Erand* is described as a *Rakta* and *Sweta*.

- There Are 5 Types of *Guggulu* is described, which is *Neela, Padma, Kumuda, Mahisha, Hatak*.
- There are 3 types of *Punarnava* described in this text.
- There are 2 types of *Aparajita* is described which is *Sweta* and *Neela*.
- There are 2 types of *Tamra* is mentioned, which is *Rakta* and *Sweta*.

Conclusion:

This Nighantu has description of 233 Sloka. Here total 159 drugs have been mentioned, among those 138 drugs belonging to the vegetable kingdom and 21 to the mineral kingdom. Only Kasturi belonging to the Animal Kingdom is mentioned here. Among the mineral drugs, all mineral drugs are described except Loha and Vanga. Variety of single drugs are described here, including *Guggulu, Erand, Punarnava*, etc.

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